

Fractionation and distribution of metals in the bottom sediments of the river Damodar near coal mines area

Uday Sankar Banerjee* and Srimanta Gupta

Department of Environmental Science, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail :

Manuscript received online 13 June 2013, revised 11 May 2014, accepted 15 May 2014

Abstract : The sequential extraction procedure of metals was carried out to determinate the concentrations of metals in different chemical phases of the bottom sediments, collected from the river Damodar near Raniganj coal field region. Metal fractions were estimated by sequential extraction process as per BCR (Community Bureau of Reference) optimized three step sequential extraction procedure. Metal concentrations in extract and digests were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GBC – Avanta). The overall percentage of metal content in different BCR fractions is in the sequence of residual > reducible > oxidisable > exchangeable and the order of metals in each fractions are as follows Exchangeable : Fe > Mn > Pb > Cd, Oxidisable : Pb > Cd > Mn > Fe, Reducible : Mn > Fe > Pb > Cd, Residual : Cd > Pb > Fe > Mn. The studies have shows that the geochemical properties of the river sediments are critical in affecting the metal bioavailability. The study also shows the cadmium and lead remain with exchangeable fraction indicate dominance of the anthropogenic sources through industrial wastes and coal mines effluents. Higher Recalcitrant Factor value of Cd and Pb can be explained because of chalcophilic and lithophilic nature of these elements, therefore, indicating poor possibility of mobilization into the aqueous system. The risk assessment code as applied to the present study reveals that studied heavy metals exist in exchangeable fraction at different levels, comes under low to medium risk category and may enter into food chain.

Keywords : Damodar river, sediment, heavy metal, sequential extraction, risk assessment.

Introduction

The river receives toxic substances through a large number of tributaries and effluent channels flowing in the catchment of the river. The toxic substances like heavy metals are derived from urban, agricultural runoff as well as municipal sewage and industrial effluents. Such types of activities often result in the introduction of nutrients and potentially hazardous levels of heavy metals into the riverine ecosystem. The metallic load then undergoes different chemical changes, whereby a high degree of variation in metal concentrations occurs in the riverine ecosystem. Riverine sediment is an important source and sink of persistent contamination^{1,2}; therefore, sediment quality is an important indicator of the environmental health of aquatic systems. Contaminants are not necessarily fixed permanently in the river sediments, and under changing environmental conditions they may be released back to the water column by various processes of remobilization³. Therefore, it is important to assess and track the abundance of the heavy metals. The metals toxic

city and bioavailability depend on speciation, either in water or sediment. The bioavailability of metals, which is the amount of substance available or accessible to living organisms, is an important characteristic of contaminant evaluation. However, the total metals concentration often does not accurately represent their characteristics and the nature of toxicity⁴. So, it is helpful to evaluate the individual fractions of metals to fully understand their actual and potential environmental effects⁵. Therefore, in the present paper an attempt has been made to study fractionation of different heavy metals to determine the eco-toxic potential of metals.

Materials and methods :

The sequential extraction procedure of metals was carried out to determinate the concentrations of metals in different chemical phases of the bottom sediments collected along the river Damodar near Raniganj coal field region. The deposited sediment samples were collected by scooping with a plastic spade and were placed in plas-

tic containers, and then frozen. Sediment samples were air-dried, ground, and sieved with desired size and further analysis was carried out. Metal fractions were estimated by sequential extraction process as per BCR (Community Bureau of Reference) optimized three step sequential extraction procedure⁶. The extractant and digested solutions were diluted with double distilled water to the desired dilution factor. Metal concentrations in extract and digests were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GBC – Avanta).

Results and discussion

Distribution of heavy metals in the bottom sediments :

Heavy metals and different contaminants in the aquatic system can lead to elevated sediment concentrations which ultimately cause potential toxicity to aquatic biota^{7,8} and residues may enter the human food chain^{9,10}. Distribution of heavy metals in surface sediments of river Damodar is represented in Table 1. The sample collection points were chosen from the Damodar river with six different sampling stations near coal mines and industrialized area.

Table 1. Heavy metal content in the Damodar river bottom sediment

Sites	Metal concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$)				
	pH	Cd	Fe	Mn	Pb
S1	7.65	1.485	4859	212.354	67.923
S2	6.96	1.863	5234	251.915	72.452
S3	7.85	0.997	4253	223.825	59.345
S4	7.74	1.257	3547	198.634	68.347
S5	7.00	1.663	4265	214.596	67.427
S6	7.69	1.485	3947	234.247	69.478
Min	6.96	0.997	3547	198.634	59.345
Max	7.85	1.863	5234	251.915	72.452
Ave	7.48	1.458	4351	222.595	67.495
SD	0.39	0.303	611.0	18.654	4.378

The concentration of Pb and Fe in the Damodar river sediments in the study area ranges between 5.45 $\mu\text{g/g}$ to 31.54 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 36.54 $\mu\text{g/g}$ to 191.45 $\mu\text{g/g}$ respectively. Concentrations of Cd and Mn ranged from 5.45 $\mu\text{g/g}$ to 31.54 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 36.54 $\mu\text{g/g}$ to 191.45 $\mu\text{g/g}$ respectively. Among the analyzed heavy metals Fe and Mn are the most dominant elements than Pb and Cd. The occurrence of heavy metals in the studied river sediment is due to discharge of industrial effluents from various industries and mining waste discharge.

Correlation study :

In water-sediment systems, the mobilization of heavy metals is influenced by accelerating and inhibiting factors and mechanisms. The mobilization and distribution of metals in water-sediment systems are dependent on various physical, chemical and biological factors and processes. pH is the most important physico-chemical factors controlling metal mobilization. Changes in pH can cause remobilization of contaminants in sediments in several ways. In aquatic systems, metal cations tend to desorb/dissolve from solids as pH decreases and causes significant release of metals; as pH increases, they tend to adsorb/precipitate onto solid material. From the study it was observed that the sediment of the analysed river is neutral to alkaline in nature (6.9–7.8). Correlation analysis was done between pH and various heavy metals in river sediment samples to assess the leaching possibility. There was no positive correlation observed in the Cd ($r = -0.871$), Pb ($r = -0.562$), Mn ($r = -0.448$) and Fe ($r = -0.549$) concentrations with the pH of the sediment. Comparatively lower pH was observed at S2 and facilitate the mobilisation of metals in the river sediment. Positive correlations were observed between the heavy metals like Cd and Pb ($r = 0.850$), Cd and Fe ($r = 0.593$), Mn and Fe ($r = 0.629$), Fe and Pb ($r = 0.293$) could indicate the same or similar source input likely resulting from mine waste discharges.

Metal speciation and its retention in the bottom sediments :

The toxicity and fate of the metal contamination in sediment is dependents on its chemical forms therefore, the study of solid phase chemical speciation and quantification of different species of heavy metals is very important toll to assess the sediment quality. Metals accumulation in sediment phases are known to occurs in major forms; exchangeable (water soluble and extractable), reducible (oxy-hydroxides of Fe and Mn), oxidisable (organic matter and sulfide bound) and residual (alumino silicates and strongly bound). Generally, heavy metals in the water/acid soluble and exchangeable fractions are considered readily and potentially mobile, while the reducible and oxidizable fractions are relatively stable under normal sediment condition and the residual fraction are entrapped within the crystal structure of the minerals and, thus, represent the least mobile fraction.

The speciation of metals in the river sediments is analyzed by the BCR sequential extraction process and given in Fig. 1. Iron (Fe) is the most abundant metal in all analysed sediments because it is one of the most common elements in the earth's crust. Fractionation profile of iron

Fig. 1. BCR (Community Bureau of Reference) fractionation profile of the Damodar river sediment.

in bottom sediments of the river Damodar indicates that major portion (45.829%) is associated with residual fraction characterizing stable compounds in sediments. The metal associated with this fraction cannot be remobilized under normal environmental conditions encountered in the nature. A substantial amount (26.592%) of the fraction is associated with reducible fraction and to a lesser extent (16.433%) with oxidisable fraction. The percentage of iron in these two phases is quite variable and may be attributed due to competition between iron organic complexes and hydrous iron oxide forms. Relatively low amount (11.147%) of iron was also found in exchangeable fraction. The residual fraction is the dominant iron host in all the samples of the total concentration. The fractionation profile of cadmium (Cd) indicates that major portion of cadmium is associated with residual fraction (55.834%) followed by reducible (22.121%) fraction and oxidisable fraction (18.101%). Toxic nature of cadmium and its association with exchangeable (3.937%) fraction may cause deleterious effects to aquatic life. A significant amount of the cadmium was associated in the first three fractions and may be easily remobilized by changes in environmental conditions. Manganese (Mn), which is also abundant in nature, behaves in a different way in aquatic ecosystem. The distribution of various manganese fractions shows that the greatest amounts are

found in the residual fraction (43.773%), followed by the reducible fractions (28.023%) and oxidizable fractions (17.631%) where as the smallest amounts of manganese are associated with the exchangeable fraction (10.573%). The fractionation profile of manganese also indicates that it is mostly bound to residual fractions. However, the fraction of the manganese associated with the residual fraction cannot be remobilized under normal conditions encountered in the nature.

Fractionation profile of lead (Pb) in bottom sediments of river Damodar indicates that major portion (50.749%) is associated with residual fraction characterizing stable compounds in sediments. The lead associated with this fraction cannot be remobilized under normal environmental conditions encountered in the nature. A substantial amount (23.400%) of the fraction is associated with reducible fraction and to a lesser extent (20.273%) with oxidisable fraction. Relatively low amount (5.578%) of lead was also found in exchangeable fraction. More than 50% of the Pb was associated with first three fractions i.e. exchangeable, oxidisable, reducible fractions and may pose risk to aquatic life under changing environmental conditions. Exchangeable fraction in BCR extraction, consist of water soluble and bound to carbonate metal fractions of sediment where the metals are held by weak electrostatic force of adsorption. Change of ionic strength and pH of the water can change the process of adsorption-desorption resulting in metal uptake and release at the water/sediment interface.

So in summary it can be concluded that iron shows the highest exchangeable fraction amongst all the metal followed by Mn, Pb and Cd. The reducible fraction of metal which is the fraction bound to Fe-Mn oxides and can release into dissolved form in the reducing aquatic environments. Mn shows the highest reducible fraction followed by Fe. The reducible fraction is the dominant phase of these two redox metal because of their slow oxidation process in aquatic environment. Mn/Fe bounded in exchangeable and/or reducible fraction by relatively weak electrostatic interactions, and may release by ion exchange processes and dissociation of sulphide/carbonate phase¹¹ with the changing environmental condition. Oxidisable fraction is the fraction where metals are bound to organic matter and sulfides and can be degraded into soluble form during oxidisable environment. Pb shows

the highest oxidisable fraction amongst all the metal followed by Cd.

Residual fraction consists of lithogenic fraction i.e. aluminosilicate forms of metal which forms very stable crystals. This metal fraction is the highest in the river sediment. Cd and Pb show their highest concentration in this form. Fe and Mn show their second highest concentration in this fraction. Chalcophilic and lithophilic nature of Pb and Cd accounts for the higher concentration in residual form, consistent with earlier findings of metal fractionation¹². The overall percentage of metal content in different BCR fractions is in the sequence of residual > reducible > oxidisable > exchangeable and the order of metals in each fractions are as follows Exchangeable : Fe > Mn > Pb > Cd, Oxidisable : Pb > Cd > Mn > Fe, Reducible : Mn > Fe > Pb > Cd, Residual : Cd > Pb > Fe > Mn. The studies have shows that the geochemical properties of the river sediments are critical in affecting the metal bioavailability. The study also shows the cadmium and lead remain with exchangeable fraction indicate dominance of the anthropogenic sources through industrial wastes and coal mines effluents.

Recalcitrant factor (RF) : The immobile metal fractions in river sediments can be determined by of recalcitrant factor (RF), which determines the extent of virtual irreversible retention of metal in sediment¹³. Recalcitrant factor (RF) was introduced¹³ in this study to estimate the percentage of contaminants in the river sediment that was resistant to remobilization, and is estimated as

$$RF = \frac{[C_{\text{oxidisable}} + C_{\text{residual}}]}{[C_{\text{exchangeable}} + C_{\text{reducible}} + C_{\text{oxidisable}} + C_{\text{residual}}]} \times 100$$

According to Knox *et al.*¹³ the recalcitrance fractions of metals consist of crystalline oxides, sulfides or silicates, and aluminosilicates, which are very strongly bound in the sediment, therefore, indicates the virtually irreversible retention of metals by the solid phase. Recalcitrant factor (RF) value of monitored metals in the river sediments ranged from 61.404 (Mn) to 73.942 (Cd) indicating variability in effective retention of individual metals. The recalcitrant factor (RF) value of Pb and Fe is 71.022 and 62.262 respectively in the monitored river sediments.

The ranking of metals with respect to RF value is in the order of Cd > Pb > Fe > Mn. Higher RF value of Cd and Pb can be explained because of chalcophilic and lithophilic nature of these elements therefore, indicating poor possibility of mobilization into the aqueous system.

Eco-toxicological assessment of the river sediments in relation to metal contamination :

It is observed from the results of the fractionation study that the metals in the sediments are bound to different fractions with different strengths. The strength values of different fractions can, therefore, give a clear indication of sediment reactivity, which in turn assess the risk connected with the presence of metals in an aquatic riverine environment. According to Perin *et al.*¹⁴ risk assessment code (RAC) is a classification based on the percentage of metal in exchangeable fractions. RAC assessed the availability of metals in sediments by applying a scale to the percentage of loosely bound mobile fractions¹⁵. This was important because exchangeable, and carbonate bound fractions, which were weakly bonded metals could equilibrate with the aqueous phase and thus became more rapidly bioavailable. According to the scale exchangeable form of < 1% shows no risk, 1–10% falls in the low risk zone, 11–30% indicates medium risk to biota, whereas 31–50% is in the high risk zone.

The risk assessment code as applied to the present study reveals that 11.147% of iron, 10.573% of manganese, 5.578% of lead and 3.937% of cadmium exist in exchangeable fraction and therefore, comes under low to medium risk category and may enter into food chain. The association of these metals with exchangeable fraction may cause deleterious effects to aquatic life. Though a significant amount of the metals was associated in the first three fractions i.e. exchangeable, oxidisable, reducible that can be easily remobilized by changes in environmental conditions such as pH, redox-potential, salinity, etc.

Conclusion

The overall percentage of metal content in different BCR fractions is in the sequence of residual > reducible > oxidisable > exchangeable and the order of metals in each fractions are as follows Exchangeable : Fe > Mn

> Pb > Cd, Oxidisable : Pb > Cd > Mn > Fe, Reducible : Mn > Fe > Pb > Cd, Residual : Cd > Pb > Fe > Mn. The studies have shows that the geochemical properties of the river sediments are critical in affecting the metal bioavailability. The study also shows the cadmium and lead remain with exchangeable fraction indicate dominance of the anthropogenic sources through industrial wastes and coal mines effluents. Higher Recalcitrant Factor value of Cd and Pb can be explained because of chalcophilic and lithophilic nature of these elements, therefore, indicating poor possibility of mobilization into the aqueous system. The risk assessment code as applied to the present study reveals that studied heavy metals exist in exchangeable fraction at different levels, comes under low to medium risk category and may enter into food chain. Positive correlations was observed between the analysed heavy metals could indicate the same or similar source input likely resulting from mine waste discharges.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank Professor J. K. Datta, Professor A. R. Ghosh, Dr. N. K. Mondal, Department of Environmental Science, The University of Burdwan and Professor C. R. Sinha, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata for their valuable suggestions and cooperation throughout this research work. The authors also acknowledge the help and encouragement rendered by Mr. Jagadish Mondal, Asst. Teacher, Mohanpur High School, Burdwan, West Bengal, India.

References

1. L. Hakanson, *Water Research*, 1980, **14**, 975.
2. W. J. Adams, R. A. Kimerle and J. J. W. Barnett, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1992, **26**, 1865.
3. U. Förstner and G. T. W. Wittmann, "Metal pollution in the aquatic environment", Springer, Berlin-Heidelberg-New York, 1983, pp. 247-269.
4. U. Forstner, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1993, **51**, 5.
5. A. Tessier, P. G. C. Campbell and M. Bisson, *Analytical Chemistry*, 1979, **51**, 844.
6. G. Rauret, J. F. Lopez-Sanchez, A. Sahuquillo, R. Rubis, C. Davidson, A. Ure and P. Quevauviller, *Journal of Environment Monitoring Assessment*, 1999, **1**, 57.
7. A. C. Heyvart, J. E. Reuter, D. G. Sloton and C. R. Goldman, *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2000, **34**, 3588.
8. H. Yang and N. L. Rose, *Science of the Total Environment*, 2003, **304**, 391.
9. J. A. Cook, S. M. Andrew and M. S. Johnson, *Water Air and Soil Pollution*, 1990, **51**, 43.
10. J. Deniseger, J. Erickson, A. Austin, M. Roch and M. J. R. Clarkm, *Water Research*, 1990, **24**, 403.
11. C. Caplat, H. Texier, Barllier and C. Lelievre, *Marine Pollut.*, 2005, **50**, 504.
12. C. K. Jain, D. C. Singhal and M. K. Sharma, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2004, **B114**, 231.
13. A. S. Knox, M. H. Paller, E. A. Nelson, W. L. Specht, N. V. Halverson and J. B. Gladden, *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 2006, **35**, 1948.
14. G. Perin, L. Craboledda, M. Lucchese, R. Cirillo, L. Dotta and M. L. Zanette, "Heavy metal speciation in the sediments of Northern Adriatic sea – A new approach for environmental toxicity determination", in T. D. Lekkas (ed.), 'Heavy metal in the environment', 1985, Vol. 2, p. 454.
15. C. K. Jain, H. Gupta and G. J. Chakrapani, *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 2008, **141**, 35.

